

The Baoshan Cemetery, Jingmen, Hubei Province

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Entry tags: Divination, Chinese Religion, Religious Place, Cemetery, Tomb, China, Religious Group, Early Chinese Traditions

In ancient China burial grounds and cemeteries were not only place of veneration and commemoration, but also sites of ritualized communication and social interaction between the world of the living and the unseen realm. The Baoshan cemetery 包山 is located in present Jingmen 荊門, Hubei Province 湖北, formerly the heartland of the Chu Kingdom 楚 (ca. 1050-223 BCE). It is one of the best-preserved nuclear family burial grounds for Chu nobility. Its location, spatial layout, burial structure design, and entombed contents provide a rare glimpse into the material, religious, and social worlds of the aristocratic elite in the late Warring States period (ca. 4th-3rd centuries BCE) in southern China. The Baoshan cemetery was discovered during the mandatory archaeological survey in this area—known for its rich cultural deposits—prior to the construction of the Jing-Sha railway in 1986 and was scientifically excavated in 1987. The Baoshan cemetery is located on a ridge—a typical topographical feature of the rolling hilly lands in the region and prized burial location of high-ranking nobles of the Chu Kingdom—that is about 16 kilometers north of the archaeological site (Jinancheng 紀南城) of the capital city (Qi Ying 郢) of the Chu Kingdom roughly from 400 BCE to 278 BCE. The Baoshan cemetery consists of four tumular tombs (M1, M2, M4, and M5) that were dated to the 4th and 3rd centuries BCE. Archaeologists have identified these four tombs to be the resting place for a family of two generations headed by Shao Tuo 邵 (b. ca. 356 BCE), who, until his death in 316 BCE, was Minister on the Left (which seems to be primarily in charge of civil administration including maintaining social order and regulating economic affairs for both the nobility and common households) at the royal court of King Huai of Chu 楚懷王 (r. 328-299 BCE). Shao Tuo was buried in the largest and the only intact tomb M2 at the cemetery. The other three tombs had unfortunately but unsurprisingly been looted since the antiquity and were poorly preserved at the time of the excavation. Immediate to the north of M2, in the slightly better preserved M4, archaeologists unearthed another male skeleton of 25-30 years of age at the time of the death and entombed weapons, often used as a gender marker for males. Based on the location and remaining entombed goods, the tomb occupant of M4 was believed to be a son of Shao Tuo. No skeletal remains were found in M1 and M5 and the identities of their occupants are inferred—wife of Shao Tuo and wife of Shao Tuo's son respectively—based on the location of their tomb in relation to M2 and M4 and the remaining entombed goods, especially the absence of weapons. In contrast, Shao Tuo's tomb (M2) was not only richly furnished but also remarkably preserved, attested by 1,935 pieces/sets of exquisite grave goods and three types of manuscript texts written in the distinct Chu script using brush and ink on bamboo slips, which provide the critical information on the identity of Shao Tuo, his lifeworld, and the anticipated afterlife of the elite like him. These invaluable bamboo manuscripts are among the best preserved and scientifically excavated corpuses dated to the 4th century BCE in China. They include selected administrative documents of the Chu royal court and local governments of seven years (323-317 BCE), Shao Tuo's personal divination and sacrifice records of three years (318-316 BCE), and funerary inventory lists prepared for his burial in 316 BCE. According to the divination and sacrifice records, Shao Tuo was a fifth-generation royal descendant of King Zhao of Chu 楚昭王 (r. 515-489 BCE) and a member of the influential Shao (a.k.a., Zhao in the received sources) lineage whose immediate ancestors—great grandfather, grandfather, and his father—and himself served in various high-ranking positions for generations in the Chu Kingdom. The Baoshan cemetery was located in an area (i.e., within 25 kilometers radius) where large-scale tumular elite burials like that of Shao Tuo were abundant, clearly separating them from the cemeteries containing small to medium sized tombs that dotted around the immediate vicinity of the capital city site (i.e., within 5 kilometers radius). Baoshan M2

had a man-made earthen mound of a remaining height of 5.8 meters above the ground at the time of the excavation, which the locals nicknamed Baoshan, or “Bump Hill,” and after which the cemetery site was conventionally named by the archaeologists. Underneath the burial mound, a reverse-pyramid shaped earthen grave pit was dug with a broad upper opening (31.9x34.4m) and 14-steps gradually going down to the narrower bottom (7.8x6.85m) of the grave pit, 12.45 meters below the ground surface. Baoshan M2 had one tomb ramp of 19.8 meters long facing east. The earthen steps and the tomb ramp serve architectural and pragmatic functions of securing the wall of the large pit from collapsing during construction and transporting grave goods during the burial. However, scholars who follow the traditional ritual prescriptions recorded in the transmitted sources also contend that the number of steps and tomb ramps, which are not specifically stipulated in the ritual compendia, is an indicator of social status subjected to sanctuary rules. It is debatable whether idealized ritual prescriptions were followed, or to what degree sanctuary rules were practiced, however, what becomes clear as more tombs of similar scales like Baoshan M2 have come to light through archaeological work, they exhibit certain common architectural features and spatial designs, suggesting shared funerary traditions and conceptualizations of death and the afterlife among the high elite of the time. A box-like burial structure (waiguo 外槨 “outer casket”), measuring (W)6.26x(L)6.32x(H)3.1m, large enough to be a good sized room, was built using 102 pieces of large and small timber logs inside a smaller earthen pit dug at the bottom of the larger grave pit. This burial structure was divided into five compartments, with the middle one containing the coffins of the deceased minister and the surrounding four compartments filled with objects that had been used in his life and things that were prepared for the afterlife, for example, the administrative documents from his office and blank bamboo slips as well as writing instruments, the latter of which are best understood to be for his continuous use in the afterlife. Shao Tuo’s burial was richly provisioned. It is especially worth noting the groupings of entombed objects in different compartments and how the interred funerary lists shed light on the design of the burial space that helps us gain unprecedented understanding of how death and the afterlife were spatialized and conceptualized by the elite like Shao Tuo of the time. Take the eastern compartment as an example. It was filled with bronze vessels, lacquerware, pottery containers, and bamboo baskets that seem to correspond to items in the funerary lists: “copper vessels from the grand kitchen” (dapao zhi jinqi 大庖之金器), “wooden vessels” (muqi 木器), “bamboo utensil baskets to be placed in the dining chamber” (shishi suoyi zhiluo 食室所以置箸), and “foodstuff for the dining chamber” (shishi zhi shi 食室之食). The eastern compartment therefore may have been conceptualized as the “dining chamber” for Shao Tuo to continuously enjoy his meals in the afterlife. Similarly, the northern compartment contains items that one would find in a study or office for a literate elite like Shao Tuo: a wooden low-table, a sitting mat, small bronze oil lamps, wooden attendant figurines, a zither, writing utensils of brush and scribal scrapper, and bamboo manuscript documents. Additionally, while the southern compartment was equipped with disassembled chariots and fittings, as well as weapons that were suitable to Shao Tuo’s elite social and economic status, the western compartment was furnished with, among other things, an exquisitely designed folding bed, two sword-wearing attendant wooden figurines, and remains of textile items. In the funerary lists, there was an entry on “items for traveling to relocate [to the afterlife]” (xiangxi zhiqi suoyi xing 相徙之器所以行) in which a “foldable bed” (shouchuang 收牀), along with many types of shoes, caps, and kerchiefs were recorded. Lastly, the middle compartment was bolstered with a similar box-like but smaller wooden structure (neiguo 内槨 “inner casket”), in which three nested and exquisitely lacquer-painted coffins were placed. The body of Shao Tuo, layers of blankets and clothes, and personal items such as swords and jade ornaments were found in the inner most coffin that contained his body. The entombed objects and the funerary lists in Baoshan M2 together shed new light on the ritual process that Shao Tuo’s death and subsequent burial had initiated and the material world in which they were embedded. The most significant source of information about the religious world in which Shao Tuo lived are the divination and sacrifice records that were interred with him. It should be noted that similar divination records have been found in other tombs that also dated to the 4th century BCE in the broadly defined former Chu cultural regions in present Hubei and Henan provinces. Since the 1960s, at least 11 tombs from large-scale ones to medium sized have yielded such kind of records, some of which contained the same name of a particular diviner. This suggests that such divination was probably practiced by a wider circle of Chu elites. However, these entombed records greatly varied in numbers from several

hundreds to one single slip, partly reflecting the status of the patrons, and partly due to their different degree of preservation. The records found in Shao Tuo's tomb are by far the best preserved and thus most complete, giving us a fuller picture of not only the highly formulaic format but also the complex relations between the living world and the unseen realm of the spirits. The Baoshan divination and sacrifice records were written on 54 bamboo slips (67.1-69.6cm), containing 22 times of divinations and 4 times of sacrifices performed by professional diviners and ritualists on behalf of Shao Tuo in the last three years of his life (318-316 BCE). Shao Tuo's diviners used similar methods—cracking (bu 卜) and casting (shi 蓍)—that had been used for almost a millennium in the northern Shang and Zhou traditions. Unlike the Shang oracle bones that recorded terse information directly on the cracked turtle shells and animal bones, or referencing the hexagram interpretations as they are collected in the *Changes of Zhou* (Zhouyi 周易), the Chu divination and sacrifice was narrated on bamboo slips that focus on prescribing efficacious ritual actions to address the diagnosed problems believed to be inflicted by the spiritual world. It was common to have multiple diviners to perform repeated divinations on the same topic, usually on the same day, each proposing a course of ritual actions. For example, in the Baoshan records, a total of ten divinations were performed by five different diviners, each doing two rounds, not long before Shao Tuo's death, in 316 BCE. However, as the Baoshan sacrifice records show, not all prescriptions were followed through and only selected proposals of ritual actions were carried out. The topics of divination and sacrifice in the case of Shao Tuo fall into two categories. As Minister on the Left at the Chu royal court, diviners periodically—more precisely in the case of Shao Tuo, annually, based on the interred three-year records—divined on Shao Tuo's service to the king and his prospect of obtaining more noble titles. Then in early 317 BCE, Shao Tuo seemed to have developed some acute illness in his abdomen that prevented him from eating, and subsequently divinations on the prospect of his physical wellbeing became more frequent. Shao Tuo's illness gradually progressed and then quickly worsened toward the end of 317 BCE, and he died less in a year, in 316 BCE. Although the concerns that initiated the divination varied, these highly formulaic records show that they shared the basic mechanism of addressing the issues of concern, that is, to communicate with a broad spirit world that included not only the former kings of Chu and lineage ancestors of Shao Tuo as well as family members who met unfortunate or untimely death, but also forces of the land, especially spirits of mountains and rivers. Similarly, sacrificial offerings in a variety of manners, as proposed in their respective divinations, were given by ritualists on behalf of Shao Tuo, sometimes at different locations depending on the recipients of the offerings. What remains unclear is why the bamboo manuscripts including administrative documents and records of divination and sacrifice found in Baoshan M2 were buried with the deceased Shao Tuo in his carefully constructed and deliberately curated tomb. One possible explanation is to consider the underlying conceptualization of burial at the time for elites like Shao Tuo, which may not be the place that marks the end of a narrowly defined physical or biological existence but a site for a broadly defined social life that continuously involves actors of both the living and the spiritual.

Date Range: 400 BCE - 278 BCE

Region: Jingmen, Hubei Province, China

Region tags: China, Hebei, Jiang Han Region, Chu, Jingmen

The heartland of Chu Kingdom (ca. 1050-223 BCE) in the 4th century BCE.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Hubeisheng Jingsha tielu kaigudui. Baoshan Chumu. Beijing: Wenwu chubanshe, 1991.
- Source 2: Hubeisheng Jingsha tielu kaigudui. Baoshan Chujian. Beijing: Wenwu chubanshe, 1991.
- Source 3: Wu Hung. "From Temple to Tomb: Ancient Chinese Art and Religion in Transition." *Early China* 13 (1988): 78-115.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL:
<http://58.49.125.196:8080/cwh/4508/detail;jsessionid=FDE0EE53C71D3098A76EB526A92BF098>
- Source 1 Description: <http://www.hbwww.org/Views/ArtGoodsDetail.aspx?PNo=Collection&No=ZJ&Guid=319cae9e-5b3e-4752-ba01-84db751abd02&Type=Detail>
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.hbwww.org/Views/ArtGoodsDetail.aspx?PNo=Collection&No=QT&Guid=a0623729-5f9d-4156-8097-2790bc2aa88a&Type=Detail>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Notes: The Baoshan cemetery was discovered during the mandatory archaeological survey in this area—known for its rich cultural deposits—prior to the construction of the Jing-Sha railway in 1986 and was scientifically excavated in 1987.

Type of excavation:

- Scientific
- Illicit

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 1986-1987

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: The Baoshan cemetery excavation

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: The Baoshan cemetery is located on a ridge—a typical topographical feature of the rolling hilly lands in the region and prized burial location of high-ranking nobles of the Chu Kingdom—that is about 16 kilometers north of the archaeological site (Jinancheng 紀南城) of the capital city (Qi Ying 郢) of the Chu Kingdom roughly from 400 BCE to 278 BCE.

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Mound

– Leveling of ground

– Clearing

– Other [specify]: deep underground grave pit

Notes: The Baoshan cemetery consists of four tumular tombs (M1, M2, M4, and M5) that were dated to the 4th and 3rd centuries BCE. Baoshan M2 had a man-made earthen mound of a remaining height of 5.8 meters above the ground at the time of the excavation, which the locals nicknamed Baoshan, or “Bump Hill,” and after which the cemetery site was conventionally named by the archaeologists. Underneath the burial mound, a reverse-pyramid shaped earthen grave pit was dug with a broad upper opening (31.9x34.4m) and 14-steps gradually going down to the narrower bottom (7.8x6.85m) of the grave pit, 12.45 meters below the ground surface. Baoshan M2 had one tomb ramp of 19.8 meters long facing east. The earthen steps and the tomb ramp serve architectural and pragmatic functions of securing the wall of the large pit from collapsing during construction and transporting grave goods during the burial. However, scholars who follow the traditional ritual prescriptions recorded in the transmitted sources also contend that the number of steps and tomb ramps, which are not specifically stipulated in the ritual compendia, is an indicator of social status subjected to sanctuary rules. It is debatable whether idealized ritual prescriptions were followed, or to what degree sanctuary rules were practiced, however, what becomes clear as more tombs of similar scales like Baoshan M2 have come to light through archaeological work, they exhibit certain common architectural features and spatial designs, suggesting shared funerary traditions and conceptualizations of death and the afterlife among the high elite of the time.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– I don't know

Notes: The area in the fourth century BCE seemed to be primarily for burial, however, it is not inconceivable that smaller settlements were also present, however, no archaeological work for settlements has been carried out yet.

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: This is not applicable.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The four tombs of the Shao family belonged to two generations, which were most likely constructed over the decades.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The area in which the Baoshan cemetery located was densely used by Chu elites like the Shao family. There is no evidence or indication for them to be planned together as one burial ground but in actuality the ideal topography and distance from the capital where the elites resided may have made the area an attractive place for burials.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Sacrificial

– Social

– Memorial

– Political

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The resources and care that had been put to construct these deep-ground burials were significant, thus it is reasonable to infer that they were meant to be lasting. The fact that they survived the millennia until the archaeological excavation also attests to the intended durability.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Notes: The Shao family cemetery was abandoned after two generations due to the relocation of the Chu royal court to the north in 278 BCE, and some of the tombs suffered looting since the antiquity, however, the Baoshan M2, burial of Shao Tuo, remained intact until the scientific excavation in 1986-7.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: As a family burial ground, the communication was most likely between the living (descendants) and the departed (ancestors).

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Given the size of the cemetery, in particular the scale of the largest tomb (M2), and the high-ranking status of the deceased Shao Tuo, his burial and the family cemetery must have used a large number of laborers. However, the precise nature of such labor mobilization--whether they were privately organized by the family or sponsored by the court or the kingdom--remains unknown.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: The high ground water level and the soil condition of this area means technical knowledge and constructions skills were necessary to safely dig deep into the ground to construct the burial. The timber structures (outer burial structure and inner coffin structure) were built on site. Some of the logs bear markings for easy assemblage that were often used

by carpenters.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Prescriptive ritual texts such as *Yili* (Etiquette and Rites) whose compilation was dated to ca. 2nd century BCE indicate that the choice of a burial location was determined through divination. However, there is no direct evidence to indicate whether the Baoshan cemetery was chosen as such.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The immediate event would be the death of Shao Tuo in 316 BCE. Traditional ritual texts indicate that the site of the burial should be decided upon using divination. There is no direct evidence for such divination to determine this particular location in the case of Shao Tuo's burial.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Prescriptive ritual texts indicate that elite burials could receive gifts from relatives, friends, and even the ruler to sponsor the funeral or to be buried with the deceased. There is no direct evidence for this being the case in Shao Tuo's burial, but this remains a distinct possibility as the burial of Marquis Yi of Zeng (closed in 433 BCE) showed evidence of gifted chariots for his funeral.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Burial sites in 4th and 3rd centuries BCE often served as a dedicated space to communicate with deceased family members who joined the rank of ancestors, together with other supernatural and spiritual actors in a broad social network in which favor or punishment would be perceived as main mechanism to regulate the relations.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The Baoshan cemetery is located on a ridge—a typical topographical feature of the rolling hilly lands in the region and prized burial location of high-ranking nobles of the Chu Kingdom—that is about 16 kilometers north of the archaeological site (Jinancheng 紀南城) of the capital city (Qi Ying 郢) of the Chu Kingdom until 278 BCE.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

Notes: The Baoshan cemetery consists of four separate but related tumular tombs, from south to north: M1, M2, M4, and M5, that were dated to the 4th and 3rd centuries BCE.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: Tomb M2, burial of Shao Tuo, who was the head of the family, was clearly the largest and most elaborated of the four tombs.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The original burial mound made of rammed earth could be monumental but as it was eroded and removed over the millennia before the excavation, the remaining height (5.8meters) cannot be convincingly identified as monumental. However, underneath the burial mound, a reverse-pyramid shaped earthen grave pit was dug with a broad upper opening (31.9x34.4m) and 14-steps gradually going down to the narrower bottom (7.8x6.85m) of the grave pit, 12.45 meters below the ground surface. Baoshan M2 had one tomb ramp of 19.8 meters long facing east. The size of the grave pit was clearly large-scale if not monumental.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Field doesn't know

↳ Stone

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: not applicable

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Besides the dug grave pit deep into the ground, wooden burial structures made of timber were built inside the grave pit.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Notes: The tomb architecture itself does not have decoration, but some of the entombed goods such as the lacquer painted innermost coffin and some survived textiles bear the typical Chu decorative patterns including abstracted birds, clouds, and geometric shapes.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):
– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human:
– No

Notes: Most of the deceased in Early China, especially the elite dead, became ancestors who became part of a broader spirit world and continued to be part of the social network of the living.

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:
– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to the elements:

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (time/resources expended) treatment [Specify]:

– Other [specify]: The skeleton remains of Shao Tuo (the occupant of the Baoshan M2) have traces of ties, probably using silk ropes, on his limbs.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Yes

↳ Human:

– No

↳ Animal:

– Yes

↳ How many animals are present:

– Number of animals: 1

Notes: One young sheep/goat was found in a small pit dug underneath the wooden outer burial structure in the grave pit.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Most of the personal effects were found inside the coffin together with Shao Tuo's body. They include two swords, one wooden bow, three arrow heads, six jade disks, two jade half-circular, two jade hairpins, and extra clothes.

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

Notes: Shao Tuo's burial contained 1935 pieces/sets of grave goods, and a significant number of them were bronze ritual vessels, exquisite lacquerware, and chariot fittings, all of which were of great economic and symbolic value at the time.

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

Notes: Shao Tuo's burial, like most of the burials of the time, elite or not, also contained daily utensils, everyday objects, and foodstuff.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Not applicable

↳ Other

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

|

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Not applicable

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: This question is not applicable.

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: The deceased became ancestors and were believed to be present at the cemetery to continue to receive offerings from and conduct communications with the living descendants.

Reference: Jue Guo. *The Spirit World*. (Paul Goldin R, Ed.), *Routledge Handbook of Early Chinese History*. Routledge, 2018.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ In dreams:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Not applicable

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Spirits of natural forces such as land, mountain, and water were believed to be present in the world in general, and thus it is reasonable to infer that they were believe to be present at a burial site as well.

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: This question is not applicable.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Notes: Ancestors and other natural forces served as monitoring agents for the normative life of the living, especially the descendants. Positive and negative developments or influences for the living were believed to be bestowed or inflicted by the spirits.

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: Although there was no direct evidence for food offering was present at the cemetery, foodstuff were found inside Baoshan Tomb 2.

Reference: Armin Selbitschka undefined. Sacrifice vs. Sustenance: Food as a Burial Good in Late Pre-Imperial and Early Imperial Chinese Tombs and Its Relation to Funerary Rites. doi: 10.1017/eac.2018.7.

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: A skeleton of a young goat/sheep was found in a small pit (known as the

waist pit) underneath the outer burial structure of the Baoshan M2.

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Daily life objects:

– Yes [specify]: The deceased was routinely buried with daily life objects.

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: Not applicable

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In general purification rituals were prescribed in later systematized ritual texts when people were about to communicate with the spirits including ancestors.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: Not applicable

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: A young goat/sheep was buried inside the tomb.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Not applicable

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– No

↳ By specific individuals

–Yes [specify]: Family and descendants of the Shao family.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Not applicable

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Grave side feasting was known through transmitted and later texts, but there was no direct evidence in the case of the Baoshan cemetery.

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The site of the burial ground was likely chosen through a divination procedure, like later ritual texts prescribed. It is unclear whether divination practices were carried out at the graved side.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: The funeral rituals were clearly performed at the time of the burials, however, the scale, kind, or scale of the rituals were unknown to us except the prescriptive ones preserved in the received ritual texts.

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: unknow.

- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: unknown

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - No
 - Notes: This question is not applicable.

- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for such a living quarter at the burial site.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Notes: This question is not applicable.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Notes: This question is not applicable.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Shao Tuo's burial (Baoshan M2) contained three kinds of bamboo manuscripts: administrative documents, divination and sacrifice records, and funerary lists. However, the reason behind the inclusion of these bamboo manuscripts in the burial remains unknown.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

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